

Intersectoral Mobility Schemes in Science Europe Member Organisations

SURVEY REPORT

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January 2017

'Intersectoral Mobility Schemes in Science Europe
Member Organisations': D/2017/13.324/1

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SURVEY REPORT

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Introduction and Executive Summary

The issue of intersectoral mobility of researchers is gaining political momentum in Europe, both at European Union level and in individual Member States. By taking the competences that characterise researchers and introducing them to the public, private and not-for-profit sectors, the production of new ideas in these sectors of employment can be increased. It therefore constitutes an increasingly important part, explicitly or not, of the national research organisations' mission to facilitate greater impact from the high levels of investment in public research made by governments.

Intersectoral mobility is also a way of ensuring a professional future for PhD holders in an increasingly difficult employment context. It permits researchers holding a postdoctoral qualification who have been funded and hosted by national research organisations, and who might not find a stable position in academia, to broaden their career prospects. The scientific and technological challenges facing today's researchers are extremely complex and, in many cases, require new approaches to research and training. As research funding and performing organisations, Science Europe (SE) Member Organisations (MOs) would like to prepare researchers for these new approaches to research and training so that they are open to new forms of collaboration and are more resilient in the face of complexity and change.

The SE Working Group on Research Careers has therefore taken stock of support schemes and measures designed to encourage intersectoral mobility offered by the SE MOs. Based on an initial workshop held in Paris in December 2013, the Working Group developed a survey of MOs in order to identify existing support schemes and to provide evidence on the relevance and impact of such schemes.

The survey used a broad and previously-published definition of the term 'intersectoral mobility': *"all possible bridges that can be built between university, industry and other sectors of employment."*^[1]

The survey was carried out between 2014 and 2015 and distinguished between the following types of support for intersectoral mobility:

- ▶ direct support to intersectoral mobility with dedicated funding (that is, a physical stay in the other sector);
- ▶ joint positions in academia/higher education institutions (HEI) and industry/non-academia;
- ▶ chairs and professorships at a HEI or research organisation funded by industry or non-academic body;
- ▶ joint doctorates with industry or non-academic partner;
- ▶ collaborative research projects between academia and industry or non-academia;
- ▶ intersectoral mobility included in the general grant mechanism;
- ▶ internships in other sectors; and
- ▶ any other form of support for intersectoral mobility (to be specified).

By the deadline, 30 responses had been submitted, encompassing nearly 60% of the SE MOs. The responses represent 21 of the 27 countries within Science Europe. Of the 30 respondents, 25 MOs were able to identify specific support schemes or measures for intersectoral mobility (see Table A).

Country	Organisation	Acronym
Specific scheme(s) in place at the time of the survey		
Austria	Austrian Science Fund	FWF
Belgium	Research Foundation Flanders	FWO
Bulgaria	Bulgarian Academy of Sciences	BAS
Croatia	Croatian Science Foundation	HRZZ
Denmark	Danish Council for Independent Research	DFF
France	French National Research Agency	ANR
France	French Alternative Energies and Atomic Energy Commission	CEA
Germany	German Research Foundation	DFG
Germany	Leibniz Association	Leibniz
Hungary	Hungarian Academy of Sciences	MTA
Ireland	Health Research Board	HRB
Ireland	Science Foundation Ireland	SFI
Italy	National Institute for Nuclear Physics	INFN
Luxembourg	National Research Fund	FNR
Netherlands	Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research	NWO
Norway	Research Council of Norway	RCN
Poland	National Science Centre	NCN
Portugal	Foundation for Science and Technology	FCT
Slovenia	Slovenian Research Agency	ARRS
Sweden	Swedish Research Council	VR
UK	Arts and Humanities Research Council	AHRC
UK	Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council	BBSRC
UK	Economic and Social Research Council	ESRC
UK	Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council	EPSRC
UK	Natural Environment Research Council	NERC
No specific scheme in place at the time of the survey		
Belgium	Fund for Scientific Research	F.R.S.-FNRS
Estonia	Estonian Research Council	ETAG
Latvia	Latvian Science Council	LZP
Switzerland	Swiss National Science Foundation	SNSF
Hungary	Hungarian Scientific Research Fund ^A	OTKA

^A The Hungarian Scientific Research Fund no longer exists.

Out of 65 schemes reported, 58 included sufficient information for detailed analysis.

The measures reported do not necessarily target only one type of support; for example, collaborative research projects may also include direct support for intersectoral mobility with dedicated funding. Thus, the total number of support types is much higher than the number of support schemes themselves.

The analysis presented in this report is divided into two parts: the first part analyses general practices concerning intersectoral mobility within SE MOs, while the second part analyses the aforementioned specific support schemes. Finally, the report summarises the main conclusions and includes recommendations to address the challenges ahead.

1 General Practices Concerning Intersectoral Mobility in Science Europe Member Organisations

Main Findings

Out of 50 Member Organisations at the time of the survey, 30 responded.

- ▶ Among respondents, 25 had existing intersectoral mobility schemes in place while six did not.
- ▶ There is explicit evidence that intersectoral mobility was a strategic priority for only nine Member Organisations (five from the United Kingdom, two from Ireland, one from Luxembourg, and one from Portugal).
- ▶ Eight out of 30 Member Organisations indicated that their organisation formed part of a 'smart specialisation' strategy.
- ▶ Intersectoral mobility was very rarely formally recognised when evaluating researchers' performance.
- ▶ The impact of intersectoral mobility on the careers of researchers is difficult to measure; Member Organisations mostly quoted intangible effects such as knowledge transfer. The main tangible impact was cited as the contribution to a higher number of start-up companies.
- ▶ Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) regulations were not uniformly in place for all those Member Organisations that indicated they had intersectoral mobility schemes; where IPR guidelines were available, they applied in three-quarters of the organisations overall (not to specific schemes).

1.1 General Overview of Science Europe Member Organisations' Measures on Intersectoral Mobility

Out of the 30 SE MOs who participated in the survey, 25 indicated that they had one or more schemes in place to support intersectoral mobility. The following types of support were indicated:

Figure 1 Number of MOs with indicated type of support for intersectoral mobility

Figure 2 Number of countries with indicated type of support (out of the 21 countries represented in the survey)
Note: it was possible to indicate several types of support for one single scheme.

1.2 Intersectoral Mobility as an Explicit Strategic Priority

Thirteen of the 30 respondents indicated that intersectoral mobility is a strategic priority for their organisation; out of these 13, it is only a 'strong' or 'very strong' strategic priority for nine of them.

Table B List of organisations with intersectoral mobility as a strategic priority

	Name of Organisation	Country
Very strong strategic priority	Science Foundation Ireland (SFI)	Ireland
Strong strategic priority	Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC)	United Kingdom
	Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC)	United Kingdom
	Arts and Humanities Research Council (AHRC)	United Kingdom
	Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council (BBSRC)	United Kingdom
	Natural Environment Research Council (NERC)	United Kingdom
	Health Research Board (HRB)	Ireland
	Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)	Portugal
	National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxembourg
Relatively low strategic priority	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
	Croatian Science Foundation (HRZZ)	Croatia
	Hungarian Academy of Sciences (MTA)	Hungary
	Latvian Research Council (LZP)	Latvia

Based on an analysis of the information provided by the MOs who consider intersectoral mobility a strategic priority for their organisation, the strongest evidence was given by SFI. The organisation has two key indicators in its publication 'SFI's Agenda 2020' referring to intersectoral mobility: it aims to generate 50% of the funding for its 'Centres for Science, Engineering and Technology' from external partners

(mainly corporate R&D entities, such as companies, but also international funders such as the European Union) by 2020; it also envisages that by 2020, 50% of the SFI trainees would move to industry as a first destination, and that there would be a measurable increase in joint funding instruments (including with companies).^[2]

For the following MOs, there was strong evidence that intersectoral mobility was a strategic priority: the five responding UK Research Councils, HRB, FCT and FNR:^[3]

- ▶ The responding Research Councils in the UK placed a very high importance on impact – and in particular knowledge transfer and the involvement of research users – through their ‘Excellence with Impact’^[4] approach.
- ▶ In the strategic business plan 2010–2014^[5] of HRB, reference was made to increasing partnerships and collaborations between academia, the health sector, policy making, the health policies and commercialisation. This listed among others “enhanced partnerships between the health system, academia and industry, mutually beneficial, contributing to the ‘smart economy’ and supporting commercialisation.”
- ▶ In the framework of the ‘Europe 2020’ strategy implementation, FCT carried out an analysis of the Portuguese research and innovation system in order to identify and quantify its strengths and weaknesses. This report identified intersectoral mobility as a key problem for the Portuguese research and innovation system and for the career development of researchers. In light of this finding, a series of support measures for intersectoral mobility has been developed.
- ▶ In the FNR Performance Contract 2014–2017,^[6] the second of three strategic objectives refers to the need to “strengthen research engendering an economic and societal impact” and in particular to “promote economic exploitation of the research results and cooperation between public research and the private sector, in particular through collaboration with industry or the private sector.” The presented measures include a ‘proof of concept scheme’ and new funding measures to support public–private collaborations and possibly industrial chairs.^[7]

1.3 Intersectoral Mobility Recognised as a Contribution to Career Development

In response to the question ‘Is intersectoral mobility formally recognised by your organisation as a contribution to the career development of the researcher?’, the 30 respondent MOs were clearly divided, with 13 indicating ‘yes’, 14 indicating ‘no’, and four stating that it was ‘not applicable’.

Those respondents replying ‘yes’ to this question largely provided relatively imprecise statements on the recognition of intersectoral mobility within their organisations. Most of these MOs appeared to have a reference in their guidelines, but the answers to the survey suggested that it was not generally monitored beyond this.

There were few institutions that specifically indicated that intersectoral mobility should be considered when assessing researchers’ past performance. Considering all the responses provided, the general situation was that intersectoral mobility was not widely recognised or taken into consideration when evaluating performance. The long- or medium-term outcome of intersectoral mobility, reflected by research experience and outputs (for example, patents, know-how, expertise) was certainly valued, but mobility per se was less frequently considered directly as an asset.

1.4 Impact of Intersectoral Mobility

Eleven MOs acknowledged a specific impact and value of intersectoral mobility on the careers of researchers at different levels, and also commented on the potential impact it had.

Table C Answers provided to highlight impact of intersectoral mobility support

Organisation	Answer
ESRC	An evaluation of the internship scheme found that the majority of internship award holders considered that it helped them to develop the ability to communicate with non-academic audiences and establish external links from their research. ^[8]
EPSRC	iCASE and EngD, both of which are doctoral training mechanisms involving collaboration with an external research partner, have been reviewed on a regular basis since their inception.
FCT	In Portugal, some studies show the impact of intersectoral mobility, mainly in biotechnology and science-based start-ups.
AHRC	See 'Hidden Connections report'. ^[9]
BBSRC	Evaluation of the Biotechnology YES (Young Entrepreneur Scheme) ^[10] and Industrial CASE (collaborative studentships scheme) ^[11]
HRB	Some of the schemes listed under Measures 1–3 are at a too early stage to be evaluated. Some informal observations for the National SpR Academic fellowship programme ^[12] exist. The aim of the scheme is to train young clinicians with high potential to become leaders in the field and to continue to work in academic hospitals. Some of these individuals have completed the fellowship successfully and are currently starting their employment with joint appointments between the academic research institution and a public or private hospital.
NERC	See 2016 Vitae survey report on intersectoral mobility 'What Do Research Staff Do Next?' ^[13]
MTA	The Hungarian Academy of Sciences (MTA) is obliged to produce annual and biennial reports to the Government and to the Parliament respectively. In these reports intersectoral aspects are presented in details. ^[14]
NCN	The problem of an impact of intersectoral mobility was mentioned in the 'Report on the mobility of Polish researchers' (2013) prepared by the Academy of Young Researchers (Polish Academy of Sciences). It said that intersectoral mobility must be increased, and thanks to such programmes as Top500 Innovators (launched by the National Centre for Research and Development ^[15] or Brokers of Innovation (developed by Polish Ministry of Science and Higher Education) it is increasing.
FWO	For the region of Flanders: Expertise Centre for the Monitoring of Research and Development (ECOOM), publication: 'Doctoraatstrajecten in Vlaanderen: 20 jaar investeren in kennispotentieel'. ^[16]

In summary, it is difficult to identify the quantifiable impact arising from intersectoral mobility measures; there are however more intangible impacts, for example through:

- ▶ promoting innovation and knowledge transfer among researchers;
- ▶ increasing communication with non-academic audiences and establishing external links;
- ▶ enhancing the development of start-ups; and
- ▶ encouraging clinical research and training clinicians to engage in academic research.

1.5 Intellectual Property

Intellectual Property (IP) is an important issue to look at when being intersectorally mobile, as researchers might make discoveries that have a commercial potential or application, which would need to be clearly attributed. A system of potentially complex institutional affiliations and differing laws and regulations on IP between the country or institute of origin and the host country or institute may make this a difficult issue.

For the 65 schemes reported by SE MOs, only 34 of them answered the question of whether or not intellectual property rules were regulated (see Figure 3).

In the vast majority – 29 of these 34 schemes – the IP rules were public and a web link was provided. Where IP rules did exist, they applied to the organisation overall in three-quarters of schemes and they were specific to the scheme in only a quarter of cases.

Most of the IP rules complied with the 'Commission Recommendation on the management of intellectual property in knowledge transfer activities and Code of Practice for universities and other public research organisations'.^[17]

Figure 3 Presence of IP rules management among survey respondents

Different schemes exist depending on who is considered to be the main contributor in the IP creation and exploitation: the researcher and his/her employer – whether this is a government or a public research performing organisation – or the industrial partner. There is an ongoing trend towards co-invention and co-development of IP, where research structures shared between the private sector and publicly funded research performing organisations blur the boundaries between types of partners. Non-linear interactions in these laboratories and organisations can be formalised through the new ‘triple Helix’ model of innovation for the knowledge-based economy. Two examples are given below:

▶ **IP rights towards the employer/organisation:**

The UK and Ireland are amongst European countries where there is a pre-supposition that the employer institution holds IP rights, which gives automatic ownership to the institution; an inventor’s revenue share will depend on the country and the domain. There is a special status for PhD candidates who normally are not employed by universities but who may still benefit from the IP of their research work. These countries have developed major structures and schemes to put in place IP rules management, such as the Lambert Toolkit, and have IP managers and offices in universities and organisations.

▶ **Substantial IP rights towards the inventor/researcher:** Sweden and Norway are amongst European countries where, for specific domains such as life science or pharmaceutical research, researchers and inventors may still benefit from the ‘professor’s privilege’ or ‘teacher exemption’; that is, individual ownership of the invention by the inventor. This type of IP rules management makes an inventor’s revenue share much higher. In this case, the career development of inventors may benefit from the traditional scheme of IP management if the extra money is reinvested in the research business or the development of a start-up business, or the like.

In some cases of IP management, there is an intermediate scheme where the balance shifts from employer to inventor after some time if the employer/organisation does not take any action to promote the invention. After this transition period, the inventor gains full ownership of the invention. This type of regulation may encourage organisations not to delay advancement of the technology and knowledge transfer but to manage their IP portfolio in a dynamic manner.

2 Specific Intersectoral Mobility Support Schemes

Main Findings

- ▶ In total, 65 schemes were indicated (details were not provided for seven of these).
- ▶ The remaining 58 schemes provided information that covered 94 entries of types of intersectoral mobility (since several types could be indicated per scheme).
- ▶ The most frequent type of support was for collaborative research projects between different sectors (24 schemes), followed by direct mobility (23 schemes) and by joint doctorates (13 schemes).
- ▶ There were 31 schemes that targeted career support, of which doctoral training was the most frequent (13 schemes) and the R4 career stage (joint professorship or similar) was least represented (four cases only); six schemes specifically targeted mobility between clinical and academic research.
- ▶ A very high number of new support schemes was introduced between 2010 and 2013 which seemed to indicate a trend towards more of these schemes in the future.
- ▶ 23 schemes indicated that the funder received an in-cash contribution from the partner from the other sector, of which 12 were in the private sector. The in-cash contribution ranged from 10% to 70% of the total project funding.
- ▶ 11 schemes were indicated to be the main support measures for intersectoral mobility in a particular region/country. These concerned measures from the UK, Ireland, Portugal, Luxembourg and France.
- ▶ 44 schemes were said to encounter high or reasonable interest from partners from the private sector or other sectors than academia. Ten out of 14 schemes in which enterprises or the non-academic sector showed a high interest were from the UK or Ireland.
- ▶ For only ten schemes the typical size of a project in the scheme was greater than €500,000.
- ▶ There was a correlation between the size of a project and the availability of IPR guidelines: eight out of the ten schemes for which the typical size was greater than €500,000 indicated that they have IPR guidelines.
- ▶ For five out of 58 schemes, gender-specific issues were reported, in particular the very low share of women in the scheme; it was notable that female participation and success rates were not systematically monitored.
- ▶ Monitoring and follow-up indicators were very diverse for the same type of schemes across different organisations.
- ▶ Only 50% of the schemes foresaw training as eligible costs.

2.1 Types of Intersectoral Support Schemes

This section summarises the survey results of the 25 SE MOs who reported on their intersectoral mobility support schemes. In total 65 schemes are indicated, but for seven of these insufficient detail was provided for analysis. The remaining 58 schemes indicated a number of different main objectives, listed in Figure 4.

It is important to note that for each scheme it was possible to list one or more types of support: for example, a collaborative research project comprising a direct mobility period in the other sector, or a measure that was aimed at training PhD researchers or support post-doctoral researchers also included an element of intersectoral mobility. Thus, the 58 schemes reported in the survey covered multiple types of support (94).

Interestingly, 15 out of the 58 measures were from the UK and six were from Ireland; with a total of 21 measures between them, these two countries accounted for more than a third of the described measures.

The key observations from the analysis of the 58 measures are:

- ▶ **Career-support schemes** were the most recurrent mechanisms being reported in 31 answers; the related types of support ranged from career stages R1 to R4.^[20] The R1 category (corresponding to **doctoral training**) was by far the most represented, with a total of 13 types of support dedicated to joint doctorates, while the senior career stage R4, with joint chairs/ professorships, only had four support types. Some measures targeted specific groups, such as clinicians (six responses) and teachers (one response), which are difficult to fit within the research career classification R1 to R4.
- ▶ The two second largest categories of support types were:
 - **Collaborative research projects** between academia and other sectors (reported 24 times); and
 - **Direct support for intersectoral mobility** with dedicated funding (reported 23 times), for example when the researcher's physical stay in the other sector was funded directly by the measure; 20 of these also covered salaries during the intersectoral mobility period.
- ▶ In only in nine cases was the support of intersectoral mobility included in the generic research funding mechanisms.

Figure 4 Main objectives covered in 58 intersectoral mobility measures in the survey

2.2 Three Examples of Support Measures

Collaborative Doctoral Awards,^[21] most recently called Collaborative Doctoral Partnerships and awarded by the AHRC, are allocations of collaborative research studentships made to a museum, library, archive, heritage organisation or to a group of such organisations, to allocate to collaborative projects that support their work and objectives. The award is a collaborative doctoral fellowship. This means that the student is jointly supervised by someone in the university where the doctoral candidate is registered and by someone in the partner organisation. Collaboration is the essential feature of these doctorates. The subject matter for the doctorate is proposed in advance and supports the work of the partner organisation.

Interdisciplinary Capacity Enhancement Awards (ICE)^[22] awarded by the HRB are innovative postdoctoral fellowships aimed at building and attracting capacity into population health and health services research through a team-based approach. They enable the development of partnerships between researchers, practitioners and decision makers in policy and health service delivery. The ICE Awards initiative is a strategic initiative to encourage partnership and collaboration between the population health research and health services research communities and clinical researchers.

Applicant teams must be interdisciplinary in nature to ensure that fellows receive appropriate training and mentoring in contextual, methodological and other issues related to their work and that they develop skills and competences required for successful interdisciplinary and trans-sectoral research in population health and health services research.

Industrial Partnership Programmes (IPP)^[23] at the Foundation for Fundamental Research for Matter (FOM) provided by NWO, aim to bridge the gap between fundamental research on physics and industrial research. In these programmes, challenging problems from the private sector are linked to creative scientific solutions, in which the company and FOM jointly fund the research. The basis of this programme is collaborative research whereby staff carry out fundamental research over a period of several years in close contact with industrial researchers in areas with a good potential for innovation and challenging scientific questions which could deliver ground-breaking innovations. Companies not only value the results from research with FOM but also the quality of FOM's researchers, many of whom later take up positions in industry. This is part of a general investment whereby government, industry and knowledge organisations, such as FOM, as part of NWO, are underscoring ambitions to strengthen the Dutch knowledge and innovation system.

2.3 Year of Introduction of the Most Important Support Types in Place in 2013

Of the types of support for intersectoral mobility that were in place in schemes reported in 2013,^[24] few were already in place in 2000. Between 2010 and 2013, there was a relatively clear increase in the number of schemes, which may point to a future trend of introducing more of these support schemes.

Figure 5 Overview of intersectoral mobility schemes in place among survey respondents for the years 2000–2013

2.4 Type of Organisation Eligible for Support: Higher Education Institutions, Public Sector, Private Sector

Most of the institutions eligible to apply for funding under the indicated schemes are universities/higher education institutions (HEIs). In fact, 45 out of 58 schemes indicated a university or HEI as the eligible body to apply for funding.

In 17 schemes involving an HEI, the HEI was also partnered with an organisation from the private sector. In 25 schemes, the HEIs were not partnered with any organisation and they were the sole eligible organisation applying for funding. There are only four schemes where the sole institution applying for funding was from the private sector with no other partner. These measures all related to PhD training.

For the majority of schemes (31 out of 58), the HEI received a contribution in-kind or in-cash from one or more partner institution(s). Among these, 23 schemes indicated that an in-cash contribution by the other sector partners was provided, and particularly in 12 schemes, the enterprise/private organisation(s) provided a contribution in cash with the majority of these schemes being career-specific. The contribution ranged from 10% to 70% of the total financial costs.

2.5 Schemes Rated as Important by Science Europe Respondents

A question about the importance of the scheme at regional and or national level in the country was answered for 54 schemes, with 12 of those 54 indicating that at regional or national level the scheme was ‘marginally relevant’, and 31 indicating that it was ‘relevant’. The remaining 11 schemes were each considered to be one of the main support schemes for intersectoral mobility at regional or national level:

Table D Intersectoral mobility measures that account for one of the main support schemes at regional/national level

Name of Organisation	Support Measure	Sector
AHRC	Knowledge Transfer Partnerships (KTPs)	Arts and humanities
CEA	Coverage of intersectoral mobility included in general grant mechanism of the organisation	Nuclear energy and related (security, medicine, materials, and so on)
EPSRC	Industrial Doctorates (EngD) – a type of centre for doctoral training	Engineering and physical sciences
EPSRC	Industrial CASE (iCASE) – collaborative research studentships	Engineering and physical sciences
FNR	AFR PhD PPP (Public–Private Partnerships)	All sectors
FNR	AFR Postdoc PPP (Public–Private Partnerships)	All sectors
FCT	Joint positions between the academic and other sectors of employment – PhD programme: national/international and in an private sector setting	All sectors
FCT	Joint doctorates with partners from non-academic sectors – PhD studentships in the private sector	All sectors
HRB	Research Leaders Awards	Health sciences
HRB	Interdisciplinary Capacity Enhancement Awards	Health sciences
HRB	Clinician Scientist Awards	Health sciences

For all of the 11 schemes that were each indicated to be one of the main support schemes at national/regional level in their country, the perceived interest by the other sector was either high or reasonable, with the only exception being the ‘Joint positions between the academic and other sectors’ by FCT, which indicated the financial crisis as a reason for the low interest by the private sector. Of these 11 schemes, seven provided funding for more than 36 months.

2.6 Perceived Interest from Partners Outside of Academia in Mobility Measures

After the description of each measure in the survey the following qualitative question was asked to MOs: ‘Are enterprises or the non-academic sector highly interested in this measure?’, and the following answers were provided about their perception for the 65 schemes:

Figure 6 Perceived interest from partners outside of academia in intersectoral mobility measures

2.7 Eligible Costs: Training

Of the 65 schemes reported, in 31 cases training was considered as an eligible cost for the given intersectoral mobility measure. Training in this context pertains to a large array of possibilities: any training activity that can help a researcher adapt to sectors other than academia, such as in intellectual property, entrepreneurship, identification of transferable skills, and so on. Those schemes where training costs were not eligible include doctoral training schemes that support intersectoral mobility. This is quite surprising, given that evidence increasingly indicates that collaborations with the private or other non-academic sectors need preparation, according to existing studies (cf. the 2016 VITAE survey report ‘What Do Research Staff Do Next?’^[25] in which the Science Europe Working Group on Research Careers participated).

2.8 Answers Concerning Schemes that Involve Gender Issues

In response to the question ‘Are there any gender-specific differences you are aware of?’, no answer was provided for 13 out of 65 schemes. Only five organisations reported gender issues, meaning that for 47 of the schemes no problems were reported.

Table E Gender issues reported in intersectoral mobility schemes

Gender issue reported	Organisation	Sector	Measure
Applicants reflect academic pool: more male than female	BBSRC	Biotechnology and biological sciences	Support for People Movement Programmes such as BBSRC's Flexible Interchange Programme
Relatively low share of women project leaders in the area of engineering	NERC	Environment	KE Fellowships
Relatively low share of women project leaders in the area of engineering	RCN	All sectors	Industrial PhD scheme
Women are underrepresented	ARRS	Natural and mathematical, Technical , medical, biotechnical sciences, social sciences and humanities	Applied projects (co-financing from business sector)
Much higher female engagement	ARRS	Natural and mathematical, Technical , medical, biotechnical sciences, social sciences and humanities	Big research projects (€200,000 per year) – as an integral part of public calls for research projects

For the question ‘What is the percentage of females participating that have benefited from the scheme?’ there was information for 24 schemes:

0–39% participation:	13
40–49% participation:	4
50% participation:	3
Above 50%:	4

It is noteworthy that for 13 measures it was indicated that this information was not available or not known. It is unclear why the information was not available or whether there was any systematic follow-up on this issue.

- ▶ For only two measures was it indicated that they gave allowances for children and partners, thus reducing the family burden, and even then only in exceptional circumstances.
- ▶ There were 38 measures that took account of career breaks and part-time working in the selection criteria and 16 that did not.
- ▶ There were eight organisations that indicated explicitly that they took into account gender issues in the design of the programmes.

The following elements were taken into consideration when designing the programmes by the eight organisations who explicitly took gender into account:

- ▶ Equality and diversity strategy committed to creating a culture that values dignity at work, mutual respect and inclusiveness (all five responding UK Research Councils).
- ▶ Ensuring that women and men have the same success rates and receive the same average size of grants, taking into account the nature of the research and the type of grant (VR).
- ▶ Specific support to women after career breaks (SFI).
- ▶ Flexibility in time commitment by the researcher (SFI).
- ▶ Taking into account delays in the scientific/ scholarly careers of applicants such as gaps in publication activity due to child care (FWF).
- ▶ Considerations regarding the gender composition of the team or collaborators in the proposed project (DFF).
- ▶ General considerations, such as equal opportunities (MTA, ANR).

2.9 Selection Criteria

For 54 measures in the survey, information about selection criteria was provided. The following selection criteria were the most ‘highly taken into account’:

- ▶ Quality of the research project (32 schemes)
- ▶ Profile of the applicant (29 schemes, among which the majority of schemes that award funding to an individual (doctorates, postdocs, chairs or professorships, positions in clinical research, and so on))
- ▶ Track record of the academic or HEI partner (25 schemes)
- ▶ Potential outcome (22 schemes)
- ▶ Relevance of the project for the researchers’ career development (17 schemes)
- ▶ Track record of the non-academic partner (12 schemes)
- ▶ Prior intersectoral mobility experience of researchers (five schemes)

Other additional but less relevant selection criteria included:

- ▶ Added value of government funding (could the project be funded elsewhere?)
- ▶ Amount of external co-financing
- ▶ Conditions for integration
- ▶ Ability to mobilise international networks
- ▶ Recruitment strategy
- ▶ Management structure of the programme
- ▶ Suitability of training plan in place for students

“Evidence increasingly indicates that collaborations with the private or other non-academic sectors need preparation”

2.10 Requirements for the Representation of Sectors at Selection or Recruitment Stage

Only 15 out of 65 schemes required the representation of other sectors at selection or recruitment stage; for 39 schemes, there were no such requirements, and for 11 there was no indication either way.

Table F Responses related to 15 schemes that have requirements for representation of the other sector at selection or recruitment stage

Organisation	Scheme	Response
HRB	Clinician Scientist Awards	The Health Service Executive (HSE) in Ireland was endorsing each application at expression of interest stage, and a representative of the HSE was participating as panel member, evaluating the strategic importance of the research theme in terms of fit with institutional and health service strategic priorities (as assessed by national strategic partners). The HSE representative also participated at the interview stage of the selected candidates.
INFN	Gran Sasso Science Institute (GSSI) assigned to INFN	—
INFN	Framework agreements between INFN and local universities	For the academy, the lack of a specific competence which can be found in the INFN
FNR	AFR PhD Public–Private Partnerships	No formal requirement, but members of the private sector are represented in the selection panel
FNR	AFR Postdoc Public–Private Partnerships	No formal requirement, but members of the private sector are represented in the selection panel
NWO	Doctoral grant for teachers	The employer of the teacher is obliged to facilitate the applicant in order for him or her to be able to do the PhD research
NWO	Industrial Partnership Programme	A collaboration with at least one company should be part of the proposal
NWO	NWO Creative Industry – Thematic Research	At least one private partner is obligatory
RCN	Industrial PhD scheme	Trade and industry
NCN	Collaborative research projects between academic and other sectors of employment	A researcher applying for the funding must co-operate with a non-academic partner

Organisation	Scheme	Response
ARRS	Big research projects (€200,000 per year) – as an integral part of public calls for research projects	In case of big applied research projects: three types of collaborating partners must be involved (university, institute, business partner)
ESRC	Collaborative research projects between academic and other sectors (Pathways to Impact)	We seek to ensure user representation (from the charitable, business and/or government sectors) on all our commissioning panels although this is not a formal requirement
EPSRC	Industrial CASE (iCASE)	It is hoped that the industrial partners will be involved alongside the academic institute with the recruitment of the PhD student
NERC	KE Fellowships	Scheme-specific, for example, fellowships focusing in a specific area
NERC	Placements/ internships available during a wide range of career stages	For specific placement/internship schemes these can be targeted at certain sectors to meet NERC's strategic needs

2.11 Evaluation of the Programmes

A total of 37 schemes out of 65 had a wide range of monitoring or follow-up indicators in place; however for 21 schemes no answer was provided to the question of how organisations evaluated the individual measure after its completion. Seven schemes did not monitor at all after completion.

Given the very high variety of monitoring activities and indicators for an otherwise relatively comparable set of activities, it would be interesting in the future to consider whether or not agreed basic monitoring indicators could be developed.

Overall Conclusions and Recommendations

The main objective of the survey on intersectoral mobility carried out by the Science Europe Working Group on Research Careers was to take stock of existing schemes within Science Europe Member Organisations in order to promote intersectoral mobility, to detect trends, and to highlight the impact of these schemes. To a certain extent, these objectives were met. This picture is, however, partial, and more investigation would be required in order to dig deeper into the issue, particularly as the need for such policies is likely to grow in the near future with the increased pressure on research organisations to deliver economic impact and to equip early-stage researchers for careers outside academia.

Although the evaluation of existing support schemes was not exhaustive, interesting patterns concerning intersectoral mobility schemes are visible. The collaborative research projects and joint doctorates, together with periods during which researchers are physically located in the ‘other sector’ (that is, the non-public or non-academic sectors), were among the most widespread types of support for intersectoral mobility among MOs. These support types can be considered as the classical or core schemes of public research funding organisations.

There were a wide range of intersectoral mobility schemes offered to researchers during their careers, from the stages of R1 (corresponding to the doctoral stage) to R4 (corresponding to professors or research leaders). The doctoral stage was the most represented in terms of the types of support available. In terms of disciplinary schemes, collaboration between the clinical and academic sectors were the most frequent among all non-academic sectors.

When it comes to the interest of the other sector, it was relatively rare that the level of interest, as perceived by the survey respondents, was high; only 14 of the 53 schemes which were covered by answers to this question were seen as highly interesting for the other sector. Ten of these 14 schemes were from the UK and Ireland. On the basis of the responses to the survey, these two countries were particularly committed to intersectoral mobility, accounting for 21 out of the 65 schemes reported overall in the survey. Both the UK and Ireland were also advanced in terms of considering IP guidelines as almost all had regulations in place.

In the reported intersectoral mobility schemes, it was relatively rare that the involvement of the other sector was required at the selection or recruitment stage. The schemes that were considered to be of high or reasonable interest typically placed more importance on this requirement. This suggests that an increased commitment by research organisations and their improved engagement with the non-academic sector leads to high interest from partner stakeholders in those other sectors, which in turn brings increased success of the measures and of the supported researchers.

► **Recommendation 1:** To maximise the success of intersectoral mobility schemes, the industrial or non-academic sector should be involved early in the process, for example when designing new schemes or for review and selection processes.

It can be problematic in institutional set-ups that involve one or more public research performing organisation and one or more private company that intellectual property is not systematically regulated in all schemes, as it can give birth to ambiguities or conflicts between partners at a later stage. Feedback obtained indicates that there is insufficient knowhow about the handling of IP, and not all organisations have in-house IP experts.

► **Recommendation 2:** Organisations running intersectoral mobility schemes should consider developing transparent IP rules; those with limited experience can learn from those who already have substantial experience in the domain.

Concerning eligible costs, in only around half of the measures were training costs considered eligible. The Working Group on Research Careers considered that preparing researchers for new challenges that originate from more regular interaction between sectors is essential in order to increase their employability and enhance opportunities for knowledge transfer and valorisation of research results. Thus if researchers are expected to interact more with the private sector, training in the professional handling of IPR matters should be a standard component of any research training agenda at the level of PhDs and postdoctoral researchers. The same is true for entrepreneurship courses.

- ▶ **Recommendation 3:** Organisations should prepare researchers for intersectoral mobility and the cultural change it involves through adequate training, in particular regarding 'soft skills', communication, the handling of IPR, and entrepreneurship. This recommendation is supported by the findings of the aforementioned 2016 VITAE survey report 'What do researchers do next?' in which Science Europe participated.

Currently, few organisations have intersectoral mobility as an explicit component of their strategic documents, but given the high relevance of innovation-related indicators in the monitoring of Horizon 2020 this will likely change in the future. The intersectoral mobility support schemes in place at the time of the survey were largely recent, pointing to a dynamic of new schemes. Thus, it is the perception of the Working Group that there will probably be a high number of new schemes in the future.

It might therefore be interesting to monitor existing and new schemes between 2015 and 2020, for example at the level of SE MOs. It could be useful to consider developing joint indicators for this monitoring exercise, in order to produce comparable information. This is particularly interesting since the types of schemes are often similar, whilst monitoring indicators are not.

So far, there is little evidence of recognition for intersectoral mobility when assessing researchers' potential contributions to the research system. If more researchers are to be encouraged to opt for intersectoral collaborations, the impact on their careers should be positive; at the very least they should not be treated unfairly should they publish less due to IPR rules.

- ▶ **Recommendation 4:** Research Organisations should introduce policies to consider intersectoral mobility in researchers' careers as something positive, so that researchers are not disadvantaged if they publish less due to their mobility in the private sector, where instead they gain a lot of other experience useful for the research system, such as handling of IPR and knowledge concerning the valorisation of research results for industrial or other commercial purposes.

When it comes to gender issues, intersectoral support schemes indicated a particularly low representation of women. What is even more surprising is that gender statistics often were not available.

- ▶ **Recommendation 5:** It should be common practice to systematically monitor gender statistics in all support schemes; this will help in developing appropriate measures in the future to enhance participation in specific types of schemes where a gender is underrepresented.

To conclude, this survey has shown in particular that intersectoral mobility schemes are not yet common practice among the majority of SE MOs. While MOs' main mission is public sector support, engagement in intersectoral collaborations and researchers mobility will be probably take a more important place in the future.

Considering more interactions and coherent links with other funders that support the private sector might be an interesting approach in the future, in order to truly enhance intersectoral collaborations and mobility, by taking into account the needs of the other sectors when defining new support schemes.

Notes and References

- [1] Intersectoral Mobility, by Karen Vandervelde; Report from the 2014 ERAC mutual learning workshop on Human Resources and Mobility, Brussels, March 26, 2014; https://cdn1.euraxess.org/sites/default/files/policy_library/report-intersectoral-mobility.pdf
- [2] See SFI Agenda 2020, pp. 17–20: <http://www.sfi.ie/assets/files/downloads/News%20and%20Events/AGENDA%202020.pdf>
- [3] Research Councils UK (RCUK) is the strategic partnership of the UK's seven Research Councils. Five of these Research Councils have answered this survey: AHRC, BBSRC, ESRC, EPSRC, and NERC.
- [4] <http://www.rcuk.ac.uk/innovation/impact/>
- [5] http://www.hrb.ie/uploads/tx_hrbpublications/HRB_Strategy_2010-2014_01.pdf
- [6] See FNR's 4-year contract 2014–2017 with the government, page 9: <http://www.fnr.lu/about-us/organisation>
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- [8] <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/catapult-centres-hauser-review-recommendations>
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- [14] <http://www.parlament.hu/irom39/13472/13472.pdf> – in Hungarian
- [15] <http://top500innovators.org/english>
- [16] See <https://www.ecoom.be/en/node/272> – in Dutch.
 For Belgium: 'Careers of Doctorate Holders Survey 2010', see
<http://www.belspo.be/belspo/scienceconnection/012/careersdoctorateholders.pdf> - in English
- [17] http://ec.europa.eu/invest-in-research/pdf/download_en/ip_recommendation.pdf
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- [22] <http://www.hrb.ie/research-strategy-funding/grants-and-fellowships/hrb-grants-and-fellowships/grant/131/>
- [23] http://www.fom.nl/live/valorisatie_en_industrie/artikel.pag?objectnumber=83419
- [24] As the survey was conducted in 2014–2015, the last full calendar year before the survey was 2013.
- [25] <https://www.vitae.ac.uk/impact-and-evaluation/what-do-researchers-do/WDRSDN>
- [26] www.bbsrc.ac.uk/FLIP
- [27] Intersectoral Mobility, by Karen Vandervelde; Report from the 2014 ERAC mutual learning workshop on Human Resources and Mobility, Brussels, March 26, 2014; https://cdn1.euraxess.org/sites/default/files/policy_library/report-intersectoral-mobility.pdf

Introduction

In Europe, the theme of intersectoral mobility of researchers is high on the agenda in all member states. Science Europe (SE) members have developed a broad range of support measures some of which have been running for some time, but the majority seem to be relatively recent.

The present survey conducted by the Science Europe Working Group on Research Careers has two major objectives:

1. The first section shall collect updated information about funding and support measures for intersectoral mobility by SE members and thereby allow to analyse trends and exchange experiences;
2. The second survey section shall address the impact of such measures.

Science Europe members are research performing and research funding organisations from all over Europe. Therefore, SE is well placed to capture trends at regional and national level that may add value to the current discussions, in particular in the framework of the ERA monitoring, contributing to an improved understanding and alignment of each other's activities and roles.

Definition 'Intersectoral Mobility'

"In its most narrow sense, (...) the term 'intersectoral mobility' is defined as the physical mobility of researchers from one sector (academia in particular) to another (industry in the first place, but other sectors of employment as well).

In the broadest sense of the term, 'intersectoral mobility' refers to all possible bridges that can be built between university, industry and other sectors of employment."^[27]

In the present survey, we target intersectoral mobility measures in the broadest sense, between the academic sector and all other sectors of employment.

Direct and indirect support measures for intersectoral mobility of researchers will be explored. Examples for direct support measures include a mobility period in a non-academic environment, such as secondments, internships, dual positions, and so on. Examples for indirect support schemes include joint doctorates where part of the PhD takes place in the other sector; collaborative research projects between the academic and other sectors of employment; innovation vouchers; and so on.

The Working Group on Researchers Careers invites all SE members to take part in this survey.

Science Europe seeks one contact person to coordinate the replies for the questionnaire. It may take some time to complete the information, since it might be necessary to obtain information from different persons involved in the support measures in your organisation.

If your organisation is participating in Science Europe's working group on research careers, you may wish to engage with your representative in completing this survey – a list of members of the working group can be found at <http://www.scienceeurope.org/policy/working-groups/research-careers>.

Preliminary results from the survey on intersectoral mobility launched by Science Europe's Working Group on Research Careers indicate that there seems to be mainstream schemes that are the most widespread among SE member (such as joint doctorates, internships and collaborative research projects), but that it might be more informative to consider targeted schemes that address specific structural weaknesses in organisations or national R&D systems. We need your input to validate these initial findings.

1. Overview of Support Measures/Funding Schemes

1. Name of your organisation

2. Contact person for this survey

Name

Function

Email

3. Which measures exist within your organisation to support or promote intersectoral mobility of researchers directly or indirectly?

Please choose **all** that apply:

- a. Direct support for intersectoral mobility with dedicated funding (i.e. the physical stay in the other sector is the basis for funding)
- b. Joint positions between the academic and other sectors of employment
- c. Chairs or professorships at a higher education or research institution funded by partners from other sectors
- d. Joint doctorates with partners from non-academic sectors
- e. Collaborative research projects between academic and other sectors of employment
- f. Internships in other sectors of employment
- h. Coverage of intersectoral mobility included in general grant mechanism of the organisation
- i. Any other form of support to Intersectoral Mobility
- j. No support measure provided

4. Please explain other forms of support to Intersectoral Mobility

5. If you answered 'No support' to both questions 3 and 4: are you sure that your organisation does not support any form of intersectoral mobility?

- Yes No

6. In the design of the programme, are there explicit provisions to take into account gender aspects?

- Yes No

7. If Question 6 was answered with 'Yes', which ones?

8. If Question 5 was answered with 'No', please list up to three of the most important direct or indirect support measures for intersectoral mobility in your institution.

9. Measure 1

Type of measure:

10. Measure 2

Type of measure:

11. Measure 3

Type of measure:

1.a. Overview of Support Measures/Funding Schemes

For each of the three measures mentioned in Questions 9–11, please report its basic features and criteria by replying to the following set of questions:

12. Specific web link to the measure (if any)**13. Measure in place since**

State the year of introduction or 'before 1980':

14. Last major revision

State the year of revision or 'before 1980':

15. Main objective of the support measurePlease choose **all** that apply:

- a. Direct support for intersectoral Mobility with dedicated funding (i.e. the physical stay in the other sector is the basis for funding)
- b. Joint positions between the academic and other sectors of employment
- c. Chairs or professorships at a higher education or research institution funded by partners from other sectors
- d. Joint doctorates with partners from non-academic sectors
- e. Collaborative research projects between academic and other sectors of employment
- f. Internships in other sectors of employment
- h. Coverage of intersectoral mobility included in general grant mechanism of the organisation
- i. Any other form of support to Intersectoral Mobility
- j. No support measure provided

16. If the main objective of the support measure is another than listed in Question 15, please specify:**17. Type of organisation applying (if applicable)**Please choose **all** that apply:

- University or HEI
- Public research organisation
- Other public sector organisation
- Enterprise
- Private foundation
- Other

18. If the type of organisation applying is another than listed in Question 17, please specify:

19. How many researchers have benefitted from this measure in 2013?Please choose **all** that apply:

- <10
- 11–50
- 51–100
- 101–250
- 251–500
- >500

20. If available, please give the percentage of female researchers who have benefited:**21. Total funding committed per year:****22. Typical size of project**Please choose **only one** of the following:

- <10,000 EUR
- 10,000–50,000 EUR
- 50,000–100,000 EUR
- 100,000–200,000 EUR
- 200,000–300,000EUR
- 300,000–400,000 EUR
- 400,000–500,000 EUR
- >500,000 EUR
- Not known

23. Typical Funding DurationPlease choose **all** that apply:

- <3 months
- 3–6 months
- 6–12 months
- 12–24 months
- 24–36 months
- > 3 years
- Not specified

24. Typical duration of intersectoral mobility period of the individual researcher in the measure (if relevant)Please choose **all** that apply:

- <3 months
- 3–6 months
- 6–12 months
- 12–24 months
- 24–36 months
- > 3 years
- Not specified

25. Eligible Expenses

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Travel and subsistence
- Child and partner allowance
- Training
- Salary of mobile researcher
- Salary of other collaborators
- Infrastructure
- Research related costs
- Consumables
- Dissemination (publications, ...)
- Overheads
- Other

26. If the answer to Question 25 was 'Other', please specify:

27. Type of contribution requested from the non-academic partner

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- In cash
- In kind
- Not mandatory, but considered a plus
- None

28. If the answer to Question 27 was 'In cash', please specify the minimum amount or percentage

29. What are the selection or decision criteria and how are they weighted?

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	Highest	High	Medium	Low	No weighting applied
Applicant's profile/potential	<input type="radio"/>				
Track record of academic or HEI partner	<input type="radio"/>				
Track record of non-academic partner	<input type="radio"/>				
Relevance of the project for researchers' career development	<input type="radio"/>				
Prior intersectoral mobility experience of researchers involved	<input type="radio"/>				
Quality of research project	<input type="radio"/>				
Potential outcome of intersectoral mobility	<input type="radio"/>				
Other	<input type="radio"/>				

30. If you selected 'Other' in Question 29, please specify:

31. Do the selection criteria and ongoing processes take account of career breaks and part-time working, for example due to family obligations?

- Yes No

32. What indicators do you use to evaluate the individual measures after completion? Please indicate:

33. Are there any requirements for the representation of sectors at selection or recruitment stage?

- Yes No

34. If the answer to Question 33 was 'Yes', please specify:

35. Is the intersectoral mobility formally recognised as a contribution to the career development of the researcher?

- Yes No

36. If the answer to Question 35 was 'Yes', please specify:

37. Are there any gender specific differences you are aware of?

- Yes No

38. If the answer to Question 37 was 'Yes', please specify:

39. Do you give any guidelines concerning the handling of Intellectual Property (incl. ownership, licensing, and so on)?

- Yes No

40. If the answer to Question 39 was 'Yes', are these guidelines publicly available?

- Yes No

41. If the answer to Question 39 was 'Yes', please provide a web link (if available):

42. If the answer to Question 39 was 'Yes', are these guidelines specific to the support measure or do they apply to your organisation overall?

- Specific
 Apply to organisation overall

43. If the answer to Question 39 was 'Yes', are enterprises or the non-academic sector highly interested in this measure?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- High interest
 Reasonable interest
 Low interest

44. Possible explanation for the answer given in Question 43:

45. How relevant is this support measure at regional and/or national level in your country to promote intersectoral mobility?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- It is one of the main support measures for intersectoral mobility at regional/national level
- It is relevant at regional/national level
- At regional/national level it is only marginally relevant

2. Impact of Intersectoral Mobility, in particular on Researchers' Careers

46. Does intersectoral mobility figure as a strategic priority in official documents of your organisation, in particular regarding researchers' careers?

- Yes No

47. If the answer to Question 46 is 'Yes', please indicate where and how, and since when this has become a strategic priority. Provide a weblink to the document(s), if available:

48. Is intersectoral mobility formally recognised by your organisation as a contribution to the career development of the researcher?

- Yes No

49. If the answer to Question 48 is 'Yes', please specify:

50. Is there any evidence of impact of intersectoral mobility on researcher's careers that you are aware of, whether in or outside your organisation, i.e. past surveys or studies?

Note that we consider impact in a broader sense, monitored for example through increased collaboration opportunities between public institutions and firms, or increased knowledge about innovation opportunities, and so on.

- Yes No

51. If the answer to Question 50 is 'Yes', please specify:

52. Does your organisation form part of a smart specialisation strategy?

For the definition of the Smart Specialisation Strategy, see: http://wbc-inco.net/object/news/12041/attach/2_Ciaran_EC.pdf

- Yes No

53. If the answer to Question 52 is 'Yes', please specify its relevance for intersectoral mobility, if any:

54. Do you know any important other schemes supporting intersectoral mobility in your country?

For the definition of the Smart Specialisation Strategy, see: http://wbc-inco.net/object/news/12041/attach/2_Ciaran_EC.pdf

- Yes No

55. If the answer to Question 54 is 'Yes', please indicate the name of the scheme:

56. If the answer to Question 54 is 'Yes', please provide a weblink to the scheme (if available):

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